

COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN TEACHING LANGUAGE.**Xakimov Shamsiddin**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12527256>

Communication is a way of interaction between people during which an exchange of something new (e.g. of information) takes place. The beginning of communicative approach lies in the early 1970s and is connected to so-called 'communicative movement' in foreign language teaching during which communicative ability was set as the main goal of foreign language learning and implications of this goal were explored and described more than they had been before. Unlike traditional language-centered methods communicative approach opens new perspectives on language teaching and is rather learner-centered. (Hanušová, 2008)

As communicative approach is the current mainstream method of language teaching, there are numerous books and studies that comment on it, explore it and define it. In attempt to summarize the main principles Brown (2000) defines communicative language teaching through the following four characteristics.

1. Classroom goals are focused on all of the components of communicative competence and not restricted to grammatical or linguistic competence.

2. Language techniques are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes. Organizational language forms are not the central focus but rather aspects of language that enable the learner to accomplish those purposes.

3. Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques. At times fluency may have to take on more importance than accuracy in order to keep learner meaningfully engaged in language use.

4. In the communicative classroom, students ultimately have to use the language, productively and receptively, in unrehearsed contexts. (Brown, 2000, p. 266-267)

The existence of new approach requiring different types of in-class activities also implied new roles for a teacher. In Breen and Candlin (1980) a teacher is seen "first, as an organizer of resources and as a resource himself, second as a guide within the classroom procedures and activities" who is

supposed to enrich the class with “appropriate knowledge and abilities, actual and observed experience of the nature of learning and organizational capacities.” (Breen and Candlin, 1980, p.99) Richards and Rodgers (1991) added three more roles, namely need analyst, counselor and group process manager. The main responsibility of a teacher as need analyst is to determine his or her learners’ needs connected with language learning and respond to them in a suitable way. In the role of counselor a teacher is expected to be a model and example of “an effective communicator seeking to maximize the meshing of speaker intention and hearer interpretation, through the use of paraphrase, confirmation, and feedback.” (Richards and Rodgers, 1991, p. 78) As the group process manager a teacher is supposed to reduce teacher-centred classroom management and establish the classroom as a setting for communication during which he or she monitors and encourages.

Although it is impossible to generalize due to every teacher’s personal uniqueness, his or her teaching techniques, pupils with various needs and many other aspects, there are some phenomena appearing throughout English classes. One of them being that it is hardly ever possible to find two or more pupils in a class whose knowledge, abilities or skills are on the same level. These differences are reflected in several areas of pupils’ school lives, including communication. Even while using mother tongue, speakers show various degrees of fluency and differ in other aspects of speech.

According to Thornbury (2005), the differences between speakers are even more noticeable when it comes to speaking in another language and the inevitable lack of fluency makes pupils feel frustrated, embarrassed or anxious. Tsui (1996) claims that many learners perceive language learning not only as a process of acquiring linguistic rules or participating in communication activities but as a process in which they are “constantly putting themselves in a vulnerable position of having their own self-concept undermined and subjecting themselves to negative evaluations.” (Tsui in Bailey, 1996, p. 155)

Conclusion. It is obvious that second language learners are exposed to a considerable amount of disruptive influence of either internal or external origin which makes their learning very difficult and demanding. Learners are influenced especially by speech anxiety, lack of genuine speaking opportunities or inability to access acquired language knowledge which leads to the necessity of applying communication strategies. As for some implications this may have for language teachers, it seems necessary to create a positive learning environment, to provide the learners with as much opportunities for spoken

interaction as possible and to help them gradually develop their communicative competence so that they feel more self-confident.

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